

Effects of Dynamic Irradiation on Light-Driven Catalyzed Water Oxidation

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Abstract

Dynamic irradiation offers great potential for the enhancement of lifetimes and activity of light driven redox catalytic reaction systems. However, investigating the effect of dynamic irradiation is challenging due to limited reproducibility and comparability of different experiments caused by the large number of influencing parameters that need to be considered. In this work, the effect of pulsed irradiation on a light-driven water oxidation catalysis was studied using a modular photoreactor (MP). To ensure experimental comparability the MP was extended with a twin reactor enabling parallel experimentation under pulsed and static irradiation.

Introduction

The global demand for energy calls for sustainable ways to generate and store energy. Due to an increase in world population and economic growth, forecasts predict that the global primary consumption will increase by around 47% by 2050, compared to 2020, to $2.6 \cdot 10^{14}$ kWh^[1]. Currently, most of the energy is generated based on fossil resources. In 2019, 86% of the worldwide primary energy was produced using oil, coal, natural gas, or uranium^[2]. Considering the limited availability of fossil resources and the high associated greenhouse gas emissions, focusing on renewable energy sources instead is essential^[3]. Among the emerging technologies for renewable energy production, artificial photosynthesis stands out as a promising approach, mimicking natural photosynthesis to convert sunlight into chemical energy^{[4][5][6]}. Artificial photosynthesis for water splitting involves the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and water oxidation catalysis (WOC) to finally yield gaseous hydrogen and oxygen. A major challenge for overall water splitting is the efficiency of water oxidation catalysis (WOC), which requires the transfer of 4 electrons and is kinetically limited^{[7][8]}.

To overcoming these challenges an efficient management of light absorption and charge transfer is central. Molecular photosensitizers (PS) play a pivotal role in renewable-energy chemistry, serving as the key interface between light harvesting and catalytic reactivity in systems used for photocatalytic fuel generation^{[9][10]}. By absorbing visible light and converting it into long-lived excited states or redox equivalents, PS enable the controlled delivery of oxidative driving force required for demanding transformations such as water oxidation^[11]. However, the performance of homogeneous photocatalytic water oxidation is limited by multiple bottlenecks in the catalytic cycle. The central kinetic bottleneck arises from the electron transfer between the oxidized PS and CAT which proceeds slower than both light absorption and water oxidation. In addition, PS and CAT degradation represent critical deactivation pathways that reduce the effective concentrations of the active species and limit the overall turnover number^[12]. Stability under irradiation also critically impacts overall photocatalytic performance. Studies on common molecular PS such as *fac*-Ir(ppy)₃ have shown that, under continuous visible-light irradiation, ligand functionalization and chemical modification of the sensitizer itself can occur, ultimately leading to PS deactivation^[13]. Similarly, in the widely used [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺/S₂O₈²⁻ water oxidation system, continuous irradiation excites both [Ru(bpy)₃]²⁺ and its oxidized form [Ru(bpy)₃]³⁺. The photoexcited [Ru(bpy)₃]³⁺ reacts with the sacrificial oxidant, generating intermediates that lead to photosensitizer decomposition and reduce its effective lifetime, making light-induced degradation a major factor limiting overall catalytic performance^[8].

Recent studies showed that light-driven catalysis benefits from adaptations of the irradiation conditions. Introducing pulsed irradiation allows reactive species to relax or undergo

Figure 1: Reaction scheme of light-driven WOC using $[\text{Ru}(\text{dpp})(\text{pic})_2]^{2+}$ as CAT, $[\text{Ru}(\text{dceb})_2(\text{bpy})]^{2+}$ as PS and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ as sacrificial electron acceptor.

productive electron-transfer steps in the dark phases, thereby mitigating deactivation processes. This strategy has been shown to enhance catalyst lifetimes and overall catalytic performance across different photocatalytic transformations.^[14] The lifetime of homogeneous light-driven WOC (see Figure 1) using the photosensitizer (PS) $[\text{Ru}(\text{dceb})_2(\text{bpy})]^{2+}$ and the catalyst (CAT) $[\text{Ru}^{2+}(\text{dpp})(\text{pic})_2](\text{PF}_6^-)_2$ was found to increase through the use of low light intensities and dynamic irradiation by a factor of 10, while the energy efficiency increased at the same time by a factor of 31^[15]. For this case, dynamic irradiation conditions were realized by continuous operation of a capillary reactor, i.e. through hydrodynamic conditions that move molecules alternately in irradiated and dark zones. For the light-driven hydrogen evolution reaction using molecular molybdenum sulfide clusters such as $[\text{Mo}_3\text{S}_{13}]^{2-}$ ($\{\text{Mo}_3\}$) as promising earth-abundant catalysts a positive effect of dynamic irradiation was found as well. Optimization of irradiation intensity, on/off frequency, and duty cycle of the LED used for irradiation led to an increase of the hydrogen production by 102 % while using 25 % less energy input^[16]. Similarly, an optimization of the irradiation conditions for HER using the thiomolybdate cluster $[\text{Mo}_2\text{S}_{12}]^{2-}$ ($\{\text{Mo}_2\}$) showed that the efficiency of energy utilization can be increased by 25 % through dynamic in comparison to static irradiation^[17].

Depending on the studied catalytic system, the observed positive effects of dynamic irradiation were reasoned differently. The improved lifetime of the HER systems might be a result of charge collection on the cluster when it is irradiated and excited. Too long irradiation, i.e. under static irradiation conditions, might lead to an accelerated loss or degradation of terminal disulfide ligands, resulting in faster deactivation and therefore accelerate deactivation pathways. Sufficiently long dark times in between irradiation periods might avoid too strong accumulation of charges and with this mitigate deactivation. Similarly, photonic efficiencies are also higher with lower photon irradiance. For the WOC system mentioned above, the degradation of the PS was found to be the main reason for decreased activity^[15]. This degradation was reasoned by the formation of sulfate radicals from the used

sacrificial electron acceptor $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$. Through dynamic irradiation, the local concentration of the sulfate radicals could be reduced, eventually mitigating PS degradation. For both systems, i.e. HER and WOC, a synchronization of time scales of the different reactive steps allowed to adjust the concentration intermediates, which is possibly the key for improved lifetimes of the catalytic systems.

A profound optimization of the different reaction steps requires tailoring of the irradiation conditions to the used catalytic systems. This especially includes adjustments of the irradiation intensity/the incident photon flux, the on/off times as well as the ratio between light and dark periods. As the underlying elemental kinetics of the catalysis are frequently unknown, a systematic study of the parameter space is required. In this work, the parameter space for light-driven WOC using $[\text{Ru}(\text{dpp})(\text{pic})_2]^{2+}$ (dpp = 2,9-dipyrid-2'-yl-1,10-phenanthroline; pic = 4-picoline) as catalyst (CAT), $[\text{Ru}(\text{dceb})_2(\text{bpy})]^{2+}$ (dceb = 4,4'-dicarboxyethyl-2,2'-bipyridine; bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine) as PS and $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ as sacrificial electron acceptor was studied experimentally. To overcome limitations of experimental deviations, the performance of WOC was studied in twin-setups. In subsequent mechanistic studies multimodal spectroscopy was used to generate an understanding of the observed correlations.

Reactor Setups

Twin Setup

Figure 2: **a** Schematic depiction of twin WOC setup for parallel experimentation under pulsed irradiation (A) and static irradiation (B) with temperature and oxygen sensors for the gas and liquid phase and **b** corresponding modified modular photoreactor with oxygen and temperature sensors in gas phase (1), liquid phase (2) and bottom irradiation module 455 nm (3).

Pulsed irradiation offers significant potential to enhance both the lifetimes and activity of light-driven redox catalytic systems. The studied WOC system, using $[Ru(dpp)(pic)_2]^{2+}$ (dpp = 2,9-dipyrid-2'-yl-1,10-phenanthroline; pic = 4-picoline) as CAT and $[Ru(dceb)_2(bpy)]^{2+}$ (dceb = 4,4'-dicarboxyethyl-2,2'-bipyridine; bpy = 2,2'-bipyridine) as PS is prone to experimental errors depended on, used analytics, reactant preparation and handling, as well as the irradiation conditions. Limitations in reproducibility occurring already in routine everyday experimentation are major challenges to disentangle the reasons for observed changes in activity. To overcome these limitations, a Twin setup was developed based on the modular photoreactor platform^[20]. The following design criteria for these setups were set for the development:

- Possibility to install optical analytics for time-resolved measurements of oxygen in gas and liquid phase
- Defined irradiation conditions with the possibility to apply dynamic irradiation conditions by changing intensity, pulse frequency, duty cycle and wavelength
- Possibility to conduct simultaneous experiments with static and dynamic irradiation
- Usable in an inert environment within a glove box

The resulting Twin setup included two identical reactor setups, with independent analytics for the gas- and the liquid phase in each reactor. The two modular photoreactors were modified with openings on both side walls to allow installation of liquid and gas phase temperature and oxygen sensors for time-resolved measurements in both phases^[21]. The reactor vial (8 mL GC vial) in each reactor is equipped with appropriate sensor spots for O_2

detection and temperature monitoring glued onto the inner vial wall with silicone glue. The fibers are kept in place with 3D-printed holders. Identical LEDs (LZ4-00MA00 RGBA) were used in both setups, but independently controlled to realize static and dynamic irradiation. For the studies presented here, the LEDs were only operated with the blue emitter. The setup (see Figure 2) was photonically characterized, by radiometric measurements with an integrating sphere and two-dimensional radiometry. A maximal photon flux of 3.058 and 2.899 $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ was determined for the two used LEDs, which could be adjusted in an intensity range of 350-1000 mA, a f range of 2-1000 Hz and DC range of 5-45%.

This setup allowed to systematical assess the influence of pulsed irradiation on the reaction rate and photosensitizer stability in parallelized experiments under pulsed and static irradiation.

NINGAS Analyzer Setup

For the NINGAS Analyzer measurements, introduced by Klingler et al.^[22], the modular photoreactor was modified to fit the Raman device's sample holder geometry to create radiation conditions comparable to the Twin setup, using the same 8 mL vials and LED type. With this setup, the gas phase oxygen content in the vial's headspace could be measured continuously and non-invasively by rotational Raman spectroscopy. The setup is documented in the SI.

Multispectroscopic Bypass Setup

The multispectroscopic bypass setup replaces the 8 mL vials with a modified Schlenk flask, similar to the setup reported by Sender et al.^[15]. Oxygen is measured only in the gas phase of the flask, while the reaction solution was pumped through a bypass multi-spectroscopy circuit, which enabled simultaneous probe-based Raman and ATR-IR, as well as UV/Vis emission and transmission measurements. The multispectroscopy setup is shown in the SI.

Performance Metrics

Photoreactor performance was evaluated using the following performance metrics.

- a) The turnover number TON

	$\text{TON} = \frac{\Delta n_{\text{O}_2}}{n_{\text{cat}}}$	(1)
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- b) The turnover frequency TOF and averaged TOF_{avg}, calculated at the time of evaluation.

	$\text{TOF} = \frac{d\text{TON}}{dt}$	(2)
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	$\text{TOF}_{\text{avg}} = \frac{\text{TON}(t_{\text{eval}})}{t_{\text{eval}}}$	(3)
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- c) The external photonic efficiency ξ_{ext} using the external photon flux q_{ext} emitted by the light source.

$\xi_{\text{ext}} = \frac{r_{\text{O}_2, \text{mean}}}{q_{\text{ext}}}$	(4)
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- d) The average photon flux q_{pulsed} of the dynamically irradiated setup, that is derived from the applied duty cycle DC and q_{ext}

$q_{\text{pulsed}} = \text{DC} \cdot q_{\text{ext}}$	(5)
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- e) The duration of one light pulse t_{pulse} for dynamic irradiation, that is derived as ratio of DC and the pulse frequency f

$t_{\text{pulse}} = \frac{\text{DC}}{f}$	(6)
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- f) The dark duration t_{dark} , the time during one period T when the emitter is off

$t_{\text{dark}} = T - t_{\text{pulse}} = \frac{1}{f} - t_{\text{pulse}}$	(7)
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Parameter Space

The influence of irradiation conditions on the catalytic system was investigated by varying the photon flux–defining parameters listed in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden..** While the parameter space for variations of the electrical driving current were constrained by the available electrical LED drivers, frequency (f) and duty cycle (DC) could be varied more flexible to modulate pulse duration (t_{pulse}), with the combination of current and duty cycle determining the average external photon flux. To systematically study the

Figure 3: a) Schematic depiction of statistically probed parameter space for pulsed irradiation experiments and b) depictions of pulse with modulated LED current for a duty cycle (DC) of 25 % and a frequency (f) of 10 Hz and corresponding pulse time t_{pulse} of 25 ms.

effect of pulsed irradiation, a simple Design of Experiments (DoE) approach was implemented using the available LED driver settings. The experimental matrix (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. a**) included combinations of LED current (350–1000 mA), f (2–1000 Hz), and DC (5–45%), with static irradiation as a reference. Each pulse is defined by its period and width (**Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden. b**), where the DC specifies the fraction of time the LED is switched on within each period. High power LEDs (OSRAM LZ4-00MA00)^[18] and LED drivers (Mean Well LDD-L)^[19] were chosen based on their essentially instantaneous response to applied current pulses translating to a square-wave temporal light intensity profile during the ON segments of pulsed illumination. This allows direct, photon flux normalized comparisons of catalytic performance under static irradiation and pulsed operation with intermittent dark periods.

Table 1: Summary of experimental parameters for the Twin setup. Pulse duration is determined by the duty cycle and frequency.

Current I / mA	350, 500, 700, 1000
Photon Flux (static setup) q_{static} / $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$	1.128, 1.536, 2.081, 2.899
Photon Flux (pulsed setup) q_{pulsed} / $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$	1.190, 1.621, 2.196, 3.058
Frequency f / Hz	2, 5, 10, 18, 50, 100, 400, 750, 1000
Duty Cycle DC / %	5, 12.5, 25, 45, 100
Pulse Duration t_{pulse} / ms	0.067, 0.125, 0.25, 0.45, 0.6, 0.625, 0.9, 1, 1.125, 9, 10, 25

Results and Discussion

Comparable Reaction Conditions in a Twin-Setup

Figure 4: Oxygen partial pressure in the gas phase (left) and concentration in the liquid phase (right) over time, comparing both setups in three experiments under continuous irradiation at $I = 350$ mA.

Table 2: Triplicate reproducibility results comparing the pulsed and static setup under continuous radiation at $I = 350$ mA.

Experiment	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 3	Max. Deviation
TON _{pulsed} setup	263.6	302.1	336.1	21.56%
TON _{static} setup	278.4	315.4	342.1	18.62%
TON deviation	5.31%	4.21%	1.76%	
ξ_{pulsed} setup	$6.66 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.73 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.77 \cdot 10^{-5}$	13.93%
ξ_{static} setup	$6.54 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.61 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$5.75 \cdot 10^{-5}$	14.21%
ξ deviation	1.78%	2.11%	0.39%	

The suitability of the Twin setup was evaluated by testing the activity of the WOC system in trails of parallel experimental runs for which both setups, named “static setup” and “pulsed setup” were operated under static irradiation with an electrical driving current of 350 mA using laboratory power supplies and LED drivers at DC = 100 % as reference experiments (see Table 2). Independent whether laboratory power supplies or LED drivers were used, a maximum deviation between the 3 trails of about 20 % was found. Considering that the photon flux was found to vary by about 5 % between the two LEDs. A comparison of the results obtained in each trail shows that deviations in the measured TON were as low as 5%, similar to the difference measured for the photon flux emitted by the LEDs. The determined photonic efficiencies showed a maximum deviation between trails of about 15 %, while the

intra-trail deviation was in the region of 1-2%. The very small deviations between the Twin setups and a reasonable experimental reproducibility in the range of 10 % experimental deviations showcase sufficient reproducibility, demonstrating inter setup comparability.

To realize a common basis for data evaluation, data obtained during subsequent studies was analyzed by normalization of results with pulsed irradiation to the results with static irradiation as TON_{rel} and ξ_{rel} .

	$TON_{rel} = \frac{TON_{pulsed}}{TON_{static}}$	(8)
	$\xi_{rel} = \frac{\xi_{pulsed}}{\xi_{static}}$	(9)

The TON for each setup, TON_{pulsed} and TON_{static} , was calculated by the sum of the TONs determined in the gas and liquid phase, $TON_{gas.}$ and $TON_{liq.}$, respectively. The photonic efficiency was calculated similarly based on the sum of efficiencies in each phase, where DC = 100 % for the static system.

	$TON_{setup} = TON_{gas.} + TON_{liq.} = \frac{n_{gas.} + n_{liq.}}{n_{cat}} = \frac{p_{O_2, gas.} \cdot V_{gas.}}{R \cdot T_{gas.} \cdot n_{cat}} + \frac{c_{O_2, liq.} \cdot V_{liq.}}{n_{cat}}$	(10)
	$\xi_{setup} = \xi_{gas.} + \xi_{liq.} = \frac{n_{gas.} + n_{liq.}}{t \cdot q_{ext} \cdot DC}$	(11)

Initial Studies on the Effect of Light Intensity

Initial studies were conducted to investigate the effect of the used electrical driving current on the observed catalytic activity. The temporal evolution of the total oxygen partial pressure in the gas phase of the system as well as the oxygen concentration in the liquid phase are shown in Figure 5. In the gas phase the oxygen partial pressure first increases and then levels off to reach a plateau. The time until this plateau is reached depends on the used irradiation conditions and the utilized pulse frequency. Under static irradiation conditions, oxygen formation starts to slows down after about 2 hours. In contrast, oxygen evolution slows down later for the pulsed experiments at around 3 hours. Interestingly, the activity increases again for dynamic irradiation conditions after 6 to 10 hours before the activity decreases again. This surprising behavior might indicate the start of a second catalytic phase, a behavior that was not reported for this system previously.

Table 3: Averaged relative results of current variation experiments at $f = 10$ Hz and $DC = 25\%$.

Experiment	350 mA	500 mA	700 mA
$TON_{rel.,avg.}$	0.595	0.709	0.993
$err_{TON,rel.,avg.}$	0.086 (14.7%)	0.076 (10.8%)	0.004 (0.4%)
$\xi_{rel.,avg.}$	2.433	2.878	3.780
$err_{\xi_{rel.,avg.}}$	0.373 (15.3%)	0.290 (10.1%)	0.067 (1.8%)

Figure 5: Oxygen partial pressure in the gas phase (left) and concentration in the liquid phase (right) over time as functions of current. Pulsed data recorded at $f = 10$ Hz, $DC = 25\%$.

To cross-check this interpretation, WOC experiments were transferred to an online measurement setup attached to NINGAS Analyzer. The modular photoreactor was adapted

Figure 7: TON (left) and oxygen concentration in the liquid phase (right) over time as functions of pulsing frequency. Data recorded at $I = 350$ mA, DC = 25%.

Figure 6: TONs and TOFs measured by the NINGAS Analyzer under variation of current and pulsation at 10 Hz and DC = 25%.

to the NINGAS Analyzer to enable measurements under comparable operating conditions as for the trials with the oxygen sensor spots. With this setup it was possible to follow the temporal evolution of oxygen non-invasively in the gas phase. The time-resolved TON, calculated from the evolved oxygen, is shown in Figure 6. For similar reaction conditions as studied in the Twin setup, namely currents of 350, 500 and 700 mA, a frequency of 10 Hz and duty cycle of 25 %, no fundamental difference between the trends of oxygen evolution were observed. Most noteworthy, no second catalytic phase was observed. It is therefore concluded that the second oxygen evolution phase observed with the Twin setup is related to the Twin setup. Careful inspection of the experiments and the setup revealed a coloring of

the sensor spots installed in the liquid phase for oxygen detection (SI Fig. 2). This color change only observed during experiments with dynamic irradiation and associated to the formation of RuO-species. This comparison between a minimal invasive and a completely non-invasive technology gives evidence that the second phase of oxygen evolution is a measurement artefact stemming from sensor spots which are non-innocent during catalysis and emphasize the importance of critical cross-comparisons of catalytic results obtained with different catalytic methods.

For studying the effect of dynamic irradiation conditions on the performance of WOC in a larger parameter space, solely measuring the oxygen content in the gas phase with the NINGAS Analyzer was not a feasible option due to the limited available measurement time of the device. Furthermore, experimental handling was more complicated with the NINGAS Analyzer since operation within a glove box was impossible due to the size of the device. Consequently, oxygen measurement with the sensor spots was continued but evaluation of the performance was restricted to the period before the second catalytic phase started. This time was identified by the following conditions: (i) The system has reached a defined end-of-activity at $\text{TOF} < 5 \text{ h}^{-1}$, or (ii) the contribution of a possible second catalytically active species became significant, indicated by a peak in the TOF derivative. Whichever condition is achieved first in the pulsed system defines the evaluation time, at which the photonic efficiency is also evaluated. This way of defining an end point for the evaluation was chosen since it is rather conservative, since the light-driven activity has not stopped completely for the pulsed systems, while the activity under static conditions was typically reduced more significant, thus TON_{rel} is not fully representing the possible lifetime of the pulsed system. For some measurements under pulsed conditions with high intensity, the two catalytic phases discussed above are not clearly separated but merged. For these conditions, the chosen evaluation criteria may overestimate the system's performance where TON_{rel} is close to or higher than 1, since the newly formed catalytically active species contributes to the formation of O_2 .

Optimization of Irradiation Conditions

The influence of pulsed radiation on the light-driven system's performance was investigated in a Design of Experiments (DoE) approach to reduce the experimental effort resulting from the long experimental runs for WOC. The following parameters were varied: DC, f and the electric current I . I translates to light intensity and consequently q_{ext} .

WOC performance was evaluated based on TON_{rel} and ξ_{rel} . TON_{rel} indicates how dynamic irradiation affects the WOC performance in comparison to the statically irradiated reference system and a TON_{rel} of 1 indicates no changes in absolute oxygen evolution. Since the time-averaged photon flux for dynamic irradiation requires the application of duty cycles below 100 %, a TON of 1 would also indicate a more efficient utilization of the available photons. This effect can be quantified by ξ_{rel} , which reflects changes caused by pulsed irradiation in comparison to static irradiation. A value above 1 indicates improvements of photon

Figure 8: Top: Average TOF calculated for the activity period of the light-driven catalysis. Reference data refers to static irradiation. Bottom: TON measured for the activity period of the light-driven catalysis. (see "Initial Studies on the Effect of Light Intensity" section for details).

utilization as a result of pulsed irradiation. The mathematical definitions are provided in the “Performance Metrics” section.

An analysis of the average TOF for the period during which light-driven WOC is considered active (see section “Initial Studies on the effect of light intensity”) reveals a distinctly non-linear and multivariate relationship between photon flux and TOF_{avg} , which becomes particularly pronounced at photon fluxes above approximately $1 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ (see Figure 8 top).

Above this threshold, an increase of the photon flux does not result in a proportional increase of TOF. Instead, a strong dependency on the reaction conditions is observed across static, and pulsed operation, resulting in substantial scattering of the TOF. It can be concluded that catalytic performance cannot be described by photon flux alone and depends on the combined influence of irradiation mode and irradiation parameters. For q_{pulsed} above 1

Figure 9: Relative turn over number and relative photonic efficiency as functions of t_{pulse} and t_{dark} . Experiments performed at $I = 350\text{-}1000 \text{ mA}$, $f = 2\text{-}1000 \text{ Hz}$, $\text{DC} = 5\text{-}45\%$. The grey horizontal plane in the diagrams indicates a relative photonic efficiency value of 1.

$\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$, the results indicate that the incident photon flux is not the major governing parameter anymore, but the catalytic activity is limited by another process.

An analysis of the TON with respect to the applied time-averaged photon flux reveals that the achievable TON strongly depend on the irradiation conditions, showing deviations of up to 500 (see Figure 8 bottom).

The results of a comprehensive evaluation of the effect of dynamic irradiation conditions on the catalytic lifetime and efficiency are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10. Since the experimentally used parameters duty cycle and frequency both influence q_{pulsed} and their combination does not result in unambiguous correlations, the evaluation of the changes is based on the resulting pulse duration t_{pulse} and the duration of the dark period t_{dark} . This analysis provides insights into effect of the interplay between light-driven processes (t_{pulse}) and thermal (dark) processes (t_{dark}). Generally, TON_{rel} increases with q_{pulsed} , approaching a value of 1 when the irradiation conditions get similar to static irradiation conditions. TON_{rel} correlates positively with t_{pulse} , with a pronounced increase of the TON_{rel} for t_{pulse} below

Figure 10: 2D projections of the relative turnover number and the relative photonic efficiency correlated against the duration of the light period t_{pulse} , duration of the dark period t_{dark} and the amount of photons supplied per light pulse n_{pulse} . Lines are shown only to guide the eye and connect data points with the same time-average photon flux q_{pulsed} .

about 10 ms, while a further prolongation of the pulse duration has only a minor effect (see

Figure 11: Left: mechanistic hypothesis. Right: Schematic representation of the solvation sphere of PS before and after oxidation to PS⁺.

Figure 10). The observed increase in TON_{rel} is most pronounced for q_{pulsed} between 0.25 and 0.75 $\mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$. TON_{rel} increases with t_{dark} and interestingly, significant increases of TON_{rel} can be observed for long dark periods with durations significantly longer than 10 ms. This gives evidence that the lifetime of the catalytic system is not only determined by light-driven processes, but also by dark, thermally-driven processes.

Figure 11 left depicts the mechanistic hypothesis for the studied WOC system. Assuming that H₂O and S₂O₈²⁻ are present in excess in the bulk phase and that the overall WOC is photonically limited up to $q \sim 1 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ (in accordance with the discussion on TOF above), the following kinetic correlations are expected:

- An increase of the absorbed photon flux will accelerate the light-driven cycle, which leads to an increase of overall TOF.
- For these conditions the equilibrium concentration of PS⁺ is expected to be very low, as it is rapidly consumed by reaction with CAT.
- An acceleration of the PS cycle equally accelerates WOC and the formation of SO₄^{•-} and PS⁺. Consequently, PS degradation caused by SO₄^{•-} is also accelerated proportionally and thus, the TON, which reflects the lifetime of the catalytic system, is independent from the photon flux but given by the (constant) ratio of the rate constants of PS decomposition due to reaction with SO₄^{•-} and the rate constant of CAT oxidation.

Applying this analysis to dynamic irradiation conditions implies that the PS cycle is only driven during the light period but stops during dark period. Thus, the TON of the studied WOC is expected to be independent of duration of pulsed and dark period but only depends on the temporally averaged photon flux. For constant q_{pulsed} , the same TON is to be expected for

pulsed and static irradiation since temporally averaged concentrations are not changing, from which the same reaction rates result.

Figure 12: Relative turnover numbers and relative photonic efficiencies correlated to the total amount of incident photons.

In contrast to these kinetic expectations, an analysis of experimental data reveals a dependency of the TON on the conditions of dynamic irradiation. Interestingly, an increase of TON_{rel} is observed with increasing duration of the dark period (t_{dark}) for low q_{pulsed} of $\sim 0.08 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ (see Figure 10). Furthermore, a decrease of TON_{rel} is observed for increasing t_{dark} for a three times higher q_{pulsed} of $\sim 0.3 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ and for even higher q_{pulsed} TON_{rel} becomes independent of t_{dark} .

TON_{rel} was also found to be not clearly correlated to the amount of photons provided per pulse (n_{pulse} , see Figure 10 right), with opposing trends depending on the incident time-average photon flux. For low q_{pulsed} , TON_{rel} increases with the amount of incident photons, while for medium q_{pulsed} a decreasing trend is observed. An increasing TON_{rel} indicates that photons are more efficiently driving WOC while the reaction progresses. In general, it is observed that correlations strongly depend on the actually set irradiation conditions and not only the total number of photons supplied to the reaction system (see Figure 12). TON_{rel} generally increases with the total amount of incident photons, indicating an efficiency increase with reaction progress. These observations have the following implications on the mechanistic hypothesis:

- i) WOC is proceeding even during dark periods, which kinetically is only feasible with a sufficiently long lifetime of PS^+ (which is known), and a reasonable high equilibrium concentration of PS^+ since WOC requires 4 CAT cycles to release one molecule O_2 .
- ii) The observed increase of TON_{rel} with the incident, time-averaged photon flux gives evidence that, in contrast to the assumption of the initial mechanistic hypothesis, the

major PS degradation pathway is independent of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ concentration. According to the assumption that the formation of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ is linked to the PS cycle, the time-averaged $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ concentration would be proportional to the time-averaged photon flux.

- iii) The main PS decomposition pathway does not depend on the concentration of PS^+ . Since no deactivation of the catalytic system was observed under completely dark conditions, a light-induced deactivation pathway is likely. A direct photodissociation of the PS might be one alternative pathway.

In addition to these conclusions, it has to be considered that TON_{rel} relates the performance of dynamic irradiation to the performance under static irradiation conditions. Thus, an increase of TON_{rel} relates to a more efficient use of the incident photons. An analysis of ξ_{rel} allows to consider this effect more specifically, since the applied duty cycle is taken into account. Over the whole range of studied irradiation conditions, ξ_{rel} increases with the amount of incident photons (see Figure 10 bottom row). Hence the efficiency of light utilization increases with the reaction progress. Furthermore, it was observed that the efficiency of light utilization depends on the applied duration t_{dark} of the dark periods. An improvement of ξ_{rel} by a factor of 3.5 was recorded when extending t_{dark} from about 1 ms to 10 ms for a low q_{pulsed} of $\sim 0.08 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$, indicating a significant advantage for the overall catalytic performance resulting from dark periods. Extending this analysis to higher q_{pulsed} reveals that it must be considered that the correlation of ξ_{rel} with t_{dark} changes at $q_{\text{pulsed}} \sim 0.3 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$ and above. Following the above-mentioned assumptions, an increase of the photon flux should lead to a faster PS cycle and subsequently to an improvement of the catalytic performance. While this correlation is observed for short t_{dark} , TON_{rel} decreases with longer t_{dark} . Since ξ_{rel} follows the same trend, a less efficient utilization of the available photons is observed. An acceleration of the deactivation pathway via PS^+ , for which the equilibrium concentration increases, is unlikely since this would lead to generally lower TON_{rel} at higher q_{pulsed} , but the opposite is observed. This also gives evidence that the dark cycle is generally sufficiently fast to not limit the rate of the whole catalytic sequence. Nevertheless, the efficiency of photon utilization decreases for irradiation with higher q_{pulsed} and since also higher TON_{abs} are measured for these conditions, a limiting availability of PS is excluded.

Efficiency losses for a fast PS cycle may arise during interaction of PS^* with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ or of PS^+ with CAT. The time scale on which the effect of pulsed irradiation is observed, i.e. 1 ms and above, is in a region in which microscopic mass transport becomes important. For this time and length scales diffusion is dominating mass transport. The reaction of PS with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ yields SO_4^{2-} , $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ and PS^+ , resulting in an environment with multiple charged species in close proximity. It can be assumed that the required electroneutrality makes it difficult to separate these species locally (compare Figure 12 right). The additional positive charge of PS^+ (Ru^{3+})

further imposes electrostatic repulsion against CAT, which is also positively charged (Ru^{2+}). For high photon flux, the formation of a large number of these ionic clusters can be assumed, which in turn potentially limit the efficiency of electron transfer for both interactions, i.e. the interaction of PS^* with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and of PS^+ with CAT. For high q_{pulsed} , it might also occur that $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is completely consumed within the narrow solvation sphere. In this case, PS^* cannot be oxidatively quenched anymore, increasing the probability of unproductive relaxation.

Comparing low and high q_{pulsed} conditions, the hypothesis described above indicates that the time scales of reaction and mass transport are similar for a low q_{pulsed} and the studied time scale of dark periods are sufficient for equilibrating the concentrations around PS through which an efficient transfer of electrons becomes possible. For higher q_{pulsed} , mass transport through diffusion, further limited by electrostatic effects, is too slow to mitigate the relaxation losses. The observed high TONs at high q_{pulsed} also indicate that the efficiency loss may not result from additional PS degradation, but rather from an unproductive energy loss channel, e.g. radiation free relaxation of PS^* .

These findings imply that the studied light-driven WOC system is limited by the interaction of the light-driven cycle with either the sacrificial agent or the catalyst. While dynamic irradiation can be used to mitigate efficiency losses, the results also call for an optimization of the catalytic system to overcome limitations arising from an inefficient interaction of the involved catalytically active species. To elucidate the key limiting parameters and identify optimal parameter combinations, in-depth fundamental studies are required in the future.

Multi-spectroscopic setup

Figure 13: Normalized ATR-IR absorbance, Raman signal, UV/Vis absorbance and emittance, and oxygen pressure of WOC recorded in the multispectroscopy setup at $I = 350 \text{ mA}$. Pulsed results measured with $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$, $\text{DC} = 25\%$.

Figure 14: Derivatives of the Raman signal with respect to time and total incident amount of photons.

The multispectroscopic setup was used for *operando* studies, recording liquid phase Raman, ATR-IR, UV/Vis emission and transmission spectra, as well as the gas phase oxygen pressure with FireSting sensors. Experiments were performed for the following conditions. 350 mA, corresponding to a photon flux of $0.5 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$, with pulsed experiments at 10 Hz and a duty cycle of 25%. Measurements of the oxygen concentration in the liquid phase were explicitly excluded to avoid the measurement artefacts discussed above. The system was flushed with nitrogen until no oxygen signal was registered over several minutes before it was closed and cut off from the gas supply to avoid nitrogen overpressure in the system. Consumption of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and formation of SO_4^{2-} were traceable in both Raman, at 1074 cm^{-1} and 978 cm^{-1} , as well as ATR-IR measurements at 1276 cm^{-1} and 1100 cm^{-1} respectively.

The simultaneously gathered Raman and IR spectroscopic data show reasonable agreement of the SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ temporal concentration traces (see Figure 13), proofing the complementarity not only with respect to the spectroscopic technique itself but also to the recorded kinetic information. The $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ consumption was found to be well in line with the SO_4^{2-} formation, which is reflected by the mirrored concentration profiles of these species. Both the Raman and the IR data show a fast consumption of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ and generation of SO_4^{2-} during the first 60 min. For further analysis, the temporal derivatives of Raman and IR signal

in correlation to the total amount of incident photons were used to compare the reaction rates for different irradiation conditions (see Figure 14). An analysis based on the amount of incident photons (see Figure 14 right) was chosen since this reflects the different irradiation conditions better than the time-based depiction. In this analysis, a different temporally averaged incident photon flux is already mathematically considered and a trend following a horizontal line indicates that the reaction rate is directly proportional to the amount of photons and that photons are required stoichiometrically. As depicted in Figure 14, the derivatives of the Raman signals strongly deviate from horizontal lines, indicating that the conversion of the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ system does not depend on the incident amount of photons.

A comparison with the O_2 evolution kinetics (Figure 13 bottom left) shows that the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ kinetics are not coupled. In contrast, changes of the UV/vis absorbance (Figure 14 bottom left) follow a similar trend as observed for the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}/\text{SO}_4^{2-}$ kinetics, which gives evidence that the PS degradation is coupled to the $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ consumption. A sharp drop of the absorbance within the first 50 min indicates a fast photodegradation. For a meaningful comparison, the varying amount of photons that were incident to the reaction system has to be taken into account. For this, the absorbance changes are plotted as a function of the total amount of incident photons (see Figure 14 bottom right). If the PS degradation would be stoichiometrically driven by the incident photons a constant rate of degradation would result and with this a linear correlation between PS absorbance and the amount of incident photons would result. This is not observable in the measured data and provides further evidence that PS degradation kinetics are stoichiometrically not linked to the incident amount of photons. This leads to the conclusion that PS degradation proceeds by a mechanism independent from WOC. Since no degradation of PS is observed without light, a light-induced thermal radical reaction that runs in parallel to WOC is a plausible reason. The radical chain could be initiated by the formation of $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radicals by reaction with PS^* . In a consecutive reaction the $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radical can react with $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ to form SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{\cdot-}$ radical, which can further decompose to SO_4^{2-} and another $\text{SO}_4^{\cdot-}$ radical, which carries on the radical chain and consumes $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$. The initially high concentrations of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ favors a fast reaction of $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ with the generated radicals. After a rapid initial reaction, the rate decreases since less $\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}$ is available in close vicinity to the generated radicals, which also leads to a larger probability of chain termination steps. An analysis of the Raman data shows very stable signals of acetonitrile, from which it is concluded that acetonitrile decomposition does not play a major role in studied catalytic system.

Interestingly the changes in UV/vis emission, which reflect the availability of undamaged PS for WOC shows a different kinetic behavior in comparison to the UV/vis absorption data. A linear decrease of the emission can be observed for static and pulsed irradiation with similar slopes, which indicates that on the one hand still sufficient PS is available in the reaction

solution to drive WOC and on the other hand that the rate of (active) PS degradation after an initial drop of the emission stays constant, independent of the mode of irradiation. It can be concluded that even for irradiation times up to 10 hours sufficient undamaged PS is available in the reaction solution, which can potentially drive WOC. This seemingly opposing conclusions from absorption and emission measurements is reasoned by the significantly higher sensitivity of emission measurements and the high concentration of PS used. Furthermore, this trend gives evidence that the minimum in the UV/vis absorption measurements observed after about 60 min is not reflecting a complete degradation of PS. The observed increase after this initial phase is reasoned by an increasing absorption band centered around 600 nm, which overlaps with the band measured at 483 nm.

From the multispectroscopic analysis it is concluded that the degradation of PS is mainly driven by a light-induced thermal radical reaction, which runs in parallel to the WOC catalysis. The observed longer stability of the catalytic system under pulsed irradiation might result from an increasing probability of chain termination occurring during dark phases, which is in line with the observations and conclusions outlined for the analysis of the dynamic irradiation conditions. The multispectroscopic analysis provides experimental evidence that WOC independent degradation pathway for PS dominates PS degradation. The in operando application of multiple spectroscopic techniques allowed for the first time to assign the fast PS degradation to a light-induced radical reaction of the $S_2O_8^{2-}/SO_4^{2-}$ systems as the most probable reason. This work presents first evidence for this loss channel, which requires more detailed studies in the future to elucidate the underlying mechanisms and kinetics as foundation for the development of optimized reaction systems.

Conclusions and Outlook

The deployment of a twin-setup approach enabled direct comparison of parallelized WOC experiments under pulsed and static irradiation. A pronounced and reproducible double peak in oxygen formation in the liquid phase was observed exclusively under pulsed irradiation. Further analysis showed that this feature originated from interference between the Firesting oxygen sensor spots and the photocatalytic system, leading to the formation of additional catalytically active species, such as ruthenium oxides, on the sensor surface. This effect was identified as an experimental artefact, as it was not detected using the NINGAS system or the multi-spectroscopy setup. These findings underline the importance of employing analytical methods that do not interact with or perturb the photocatalytic system to ensure reliable and artefact-free WOC measurements. Comparison of TOF under pulsed and static irradiation reveals a distinctly nonlinear and multivariate relationship between photon flux and catalytic activity. The performance depends on the combined effects of irradiation mode and operating parameters. A comprehensive evaluation of the parameter space based on TON_{rel} and ξ_{rel} shows that the photon flux, determined by the combination

of current and DC , has the largest impact on WOC performance. With respect to TON_{rel} and ξ_{rel} pulsed irradiation approaches the performance of static irradiation under high DC , resulting in similar TON_{rel} and ξ_{rel} at significantly lower photon fluxes. At low current and DC set for pulsed irradiation conditions, ξ_{rel} increased significantly, indicating a more efficient photon utilization compared to static irradiation. Comparison with hydrodynamically realized pulsed irradiation WOC systems reported by Sender et al.^[15] suggests that pulsed irradiation alone cannot account for the reported order-of-magnitude increase in activity, but rather that this enhancement arises from a complex interplay between hydrodynamics and photonics. Nevertheless, from the perspective of photoreactor design and scale-up, intermittent irradiation conditions represent a promising strategy for improving photonic efficiency. In situ multispectroscopic measurements conducted during catalysis provided additional insight into the influence of pulsed irradiation on the underlying photochemical processes, indicating reduced photosensitizer deactivation under pulsed irradiation conditions.

Materials and Methods

Experimental Preparation

Synthesis of the PS was conducted as described in the literature.^{[30][31]} All other compounds were bought from commercial suppliers.

Preparations of all catalysis solutions used in the Twin setup and the NGA were performed under inert gas argon atmosphere inside a glovebox. $[Ru^{2+}(dpp)(pic)_2](PF_6^-)_2$ (2.6 μ M), $[Ru^{2+}(dceb)_2(bpy)](PF_6^-)_2$ (0.3 mM) and $Na_2S_2O_8$ (10 mM) were dissolved in 2 mL of an oxygen-free 96:4 (v/v) buffer:MeCN mixture and transferred into a 8 mL GC vial and sealed with an airtight screw cap.

Buffer solution was prepared using H_3BO_3 (0.08 M) dissolved in H_2O and $NaHCO_3$ to adjust the pH to 6.5. Afterwards the solution was stirred and degassed with argon.

NGA sample kept in a dark box before experiment, prepared right before experiment.

Multispectroscopic setup:

The multispectroscopic samples were prepared in accordance with the work previously done by Sender et al.^[15]. Sodium persulfate ($Na_2S_2O_8$, 10 mM) was dissolved in deionized water, while all other components were dissolved in a $H_3BO_3/NaHCO_3$ buffer (pH 6.5, 0.08 M). The final solution was a 10 mL solution containing 2.6 μ M $[Ru(dpp)(pic)_2](PF_6)_2$ as the catalyst, 0.3 mM $[Ru(dceb)_2(bpy)](PF_6)_2$ as the photosensitizer, and 10 mM $Na_2S_2O_8$ as the sacrificial electron acceptor, in a solvent mixture consisting of $H_3BO_3/NaHCO_3$ buffer and acetonitrile

(MeCN) in a 96:4 vol% ratio. Prior to Raman measurements, the solutions were purged with argon for approximately 30 min and subsequently transferred to the setup.

Empty setup flushed with nitrogen for 10 min at 50 mL/s with KNF SIMDOS® 10 FEM 1.10 TT.18 RC-P diaphragm liquid dosing pump running (until oxygen signal 0), reservoir injected with degassed solution components (total 10 mL) and pumped another 5 minutes at 50 mL/s (until oxygen signal 0) to mix reagents, Schlenk valve is closed to cut off nitrogen before experiment and ground glass joint clip attached to ground glass stopper.

Experimental Procedure

LED: Led Engine LZ4-00MA00 RGBA^[18] LEDs (only blue LED used) mounted on S-series Ohmite heat sinks (SA-LED-151E) with M3 screws and thermal paste. Benchtop power supply for continuous measurements: RND 320-KA3005P by RND Lab in Twin setup. Power supply for all measurements in NGA and bypass setup, and pulsed measurements in Twin setup: modular photoreactor controller (ref: DK paper), used drivers for 350, 500, 700 and 1000 mA

Twin setup: experiments performed in modular photoreactor^[20] in glovebox under constant argon atmosphere. Oxygen sensing started 10 min before LED turned on. Full parameter space (variation of LED current, pulsing frequency and duty cycle) measured.

NGA setup: vials prepared in glovebox, performed in modified modular photoreactor adapted to NGA. Sample kept in the dark until measurement start in NGA.

Bypass setup: degassed reaction solution components (separately: buffer, PS, cat, SA) injected in nitrogen flushed reactor, pumped through bypass under nitrogen flow to mix for about 5 minutes. Before light on: nitrogen flow stopped, reactor sealed. Performed in modified NGA adapted to larger Schlenk vial (reaction volume: 10 mL in 40.77 mL Schlenk reservoir/42.49 mL system volume). Cole-Parmer 1/8" OD 1/16" ID PVDF capillaries.

Optical O₂ and Temperature Sensing

PyroScience optical oxygen and temperature meter FireSting-O2 (FSO2-C4)

Twin setup: OXSP5 sensor spots for oxygen, TPSP5 spots for temperature in gas and liquid phase, glued onto vials with silicon glue for gas and liquid phase, two-point calibration for oxygen and temperature sensor spots, connected to FSO2-C4 via optical fiber SPFIB for readout.

Bypass setup: self-adhesive TROXSP5-ADH sensor spot directly attached to reactor (Schlenk vial) headspace, single-point calibration at 100% nitrogen, connected to FSO2-C4 via optical fiber SPFIB-BARE for readout. Environmental temperature tracked via Tinkerforge Temperature Bricklet 2.0 attached to modular photoreactor controller and via ATR-IR probe in flow.

NINGAS Raman Analyzer (non-invasive headspace rotational Stokes Raman)

To analyze O₂ concentrations during catalysis, the NINGAS Raman Analyzer was calibrated using a two-point calibration at 0% and 100% oxygen levels. This was done using mass flow controller and commercially available pure argon and oxygen constant gas flow through an empty 8 mL sample vial. The signal saturation limit of the NGA is 64.000 (signal intensity; arb. u.) and therefore the two-point calibration uses a maximum of ~45.000 with an exposure time of 15 seconds. Additionally, sample vials are heated *via* the integrated heating cartridge to 35 °C to avoid fogging of the analyzing laser pathway inside the vial.

Reference Sarah's publication!!

UV-vis and Fluorescence Spectroscopy

Fluorescence spectrometer: Avantes AvaSpec ULS3648-RS-USB2 (50 um slit)

UV-vis spectrometer: Avantes AvaSpec-ULS4096CL-EVO (10 um slit)

Light source: Avantes AvaLight-HAL-S-Mini

Optical fibers: 3x FC-UVIR600-1

Fibers connected via SMA to spectrometers, attached to capillary with holding screws in 3D printed measurement cell (reference: Sender paper, modified for UV-vis and fluorescence at the same time – Sender only documents fluorescence) → cell sketch/photo in SI

Data recorded with Avantes software, once per minute.

Raman Spectroscopy

The samples were measured using a NIR – excited fiber coupled Raman setup (RXN I, Kaiser Optical Systems, Ann Arbor, MI, USA). Samples were excited through a fiberoptic probe (InPhotonics, Norwood, MA, USA) which is equipped with band and long pass filters for cleanup and Rayleigh-rejection (cutoff long pass: ca. 250cm⁻¹) coupled to a 785 nm single-frequency laser diode (Xtra II, Topica Photonics, Munich, Germany). This system disperses the scattered Raman light passing through a holographic grating which is detected via a

multi-row, thermoelectrically cooled (TOP = -60°C) CCD (Andor, Belfast, UK) resulting in spectral resolution around 4 cm⁻¹. The system was white light calibrated using a white light source prior to the measurements and data was collected from 250-3500cm⁻¹. Raman spectra were recorded with a power of 250 mW at the sample, for 5 seconds and 20 accumulations per spectrum.

ATR-IR Spectroscopy

ATR-IR measurements were performed using the ReactIR 702L (Mettler-Toledo) equipped with a diamond DST-ATR-probe (Mettler Toledo, Gießen, Germany). The ATR-probe was inserted into the multispectroscopy measurement cell (SI REFERENCE), where the measurements were performed in flow. 139 measurements were recorded each minute and averaged during the reaction. The resolution was 4 cm⁻¹ and the wavenumber range was between 4000 - 648 cm⁻¹. Air was measured as a background and subtracted from all spectra.

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